

СЎЗ САЊАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

8 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 8, НОМЕР 2

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 8, ISSUE 2

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА | INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

№2 (2025) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9297-2025-2>

Бош муҳаррир:
Тўхтасинов Илҳом
п.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Бош муҳаррир ўринбосари:

Главный редактор:
Тухтасинов Илхом
д.п.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Заместитель главного редактора:

Editor in Chief:
Tuhtasinov Ilhom
DSc. Professor (Uzbekistan)

Deputy Chief Editor

ТАҲРИРИЙ МАСЛАҲАТ КЕНГАШИ

Назаров Бахтиёр
академик. (Ўзбекистон)

Якуб Умарўғли
ф.ф.д., профессор (Туркия)

Алмаз Улви Биннатова
ф.ф.д., профессор (Озарбайжон)

Бокиева Гуландом
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Миннуллин Ким
ф.ф.д., профессор (Татаристон)

Махмудов Низомиддин
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Керимов Исмаил
ф.ф.д., профессор (Россия)

Жўраев Маматкул
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Куренов Рахиммамед
к.ф.н. (Туркменистон)

Кристофер Жеймс Форт
Мичиган университети (АҚШ)

Умархўжаев Мухтор
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Мирзаев Ибодулло
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Болтабоев Ҳамидулла
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Дўстмухаммедов Хуршид
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Лиходзиевский А.С.
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Сиддиқова Ирода
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Шиукашвили Тамар
ф.ф.д. (Грузия)

Туробов Бекпулат
масбул котиб, PhD, доцент
(Ўзбекистон)

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ

Назаров Бахтиёр
академик. (Узбекистан)

Якуб Умар оглы
д.ф.н., профессор (Туркия)

Алмаз Улви Биннатова
д.ф.н., профессор (Азербайджан)

Бакиева Гуландом
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Миннуллин Ким
д.ф.н., профессор (Татарстан)

Махмудов Низомиддин
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Керимов Исмаил
д.ф.н., профессор (Россия)

Джураев Маматкул
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Куренов Рахыммамед
к.ф.н. (Туркменистан)

Кристофер Джеймс Форт
Университет Мичигана (США)

Умархаджаев Мухтар
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Мирзаев Ибодулло
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Балтабоев Ҳамидулла
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Дустмухаммедов Хуршид
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Лиходзиевский А.С.
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Сиддиқова Ирода
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Шиукашвили Тамар
д.ф.н. (Грузия)

Туробов Бекпулат
отв. секретарь, PhD, доцент
(Узбекистан)

EDITORIAL BOARD

Bakhtiyor Nazarov
academician. (Uzbekistan)

Yakub Umarogli
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Turkey)

Almaz Ulvi Binnatova
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Azerbaijan)

Bakieva Gulandom
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Minnulin Kim
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Tatarstan)

Mahmudov Nizomiddin
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Kerimov Ismail
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Russia)

Juraev Mamatkul
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Kurenov Rakhimmamed
Ph.D. Ass. Prof. (Turkmenistan)

Christopher James Fort
University of Michigan (USA)

Umarkhodjaev Mukhtar
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Mirzaev Ibodulla
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Boltaboev Hamidulla
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Dustmuhammedov Khurshid
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Lixodzievsky A.S.
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Siddiqova Iroda
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Shiukashvili Tamar
Doc. of philol. scien. (Georgia)

Turobov Bekpulat
PhD Ass. prof. Senior Secretary
(Uzbekistan)

PageMaker | Верстка | Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

1. Murodova Mo'tabar Ibodullayevna TILAKLAR VA OLQISHLARNI NUTQIY AKTLAR SIFATIDA LINGVISTIK NUQTAI NAZARDAN TAHLILI...	5
2. Yusupova Soxiba Islombek qizi O'ZBEK BOLALAR O'YIN QO'SHIQLARIDA ATOQLI OTLARNING QO'LLANILISHI.....	9
3. Lolayeva Gulniso Geldiyorovna GAZETA MATNINING UMUMIY VAZIFALARI.....	13
4. Sharopova Ra'no, Karimova Latofat HOZIRGI O'ZBEK TILIDA "TARBIYA" LEKSIK-SEMANTIK MAYDONI TARKIBI VA TASNIFIQA OID QARASHLAR.....	18
5. Намазова Манзура Ураковна ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ И СОЦИАЛЬНЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ЖИЗНИ И ЧАСТИ ИММИГРАНТОВ В УЗБЕКСКОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЕ.....	24
6. Sadriddinzoda Safiya Shaxobiddinovna AMPHIBOLOGY IN ENGLISH RELIGIOUS LEXICOLOGY.....	32
7. Esirgapov Mukhiddin Nizomiddinovich THE INFLUENCE OF THE INTERNET AND DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES ON THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE.....	37
8. Karimova Dilorom Shavkatovna VERBAL AND NON-VERBAL INTERPRETATION OF THE CONCEPTS OF "DEATH" AND "LIFE".....	43
9. Narzullaeva Dilnoza Sanatovna CONCEPTUAL METAPHOR THEORY: EXPLORING THE ROLE OF METAPHOR IN CONCEPTUALIZING ABSTRACT CONCEPTS.....	48
10. Шахзод Турниязов ЎЗБЕК ТИЛИГА ҚИЛИНАЁТГАН ЗАМОНАВИЙ БАДИИЙ ТАРЖИМАЛАРДА МУАЛЛИФ УСЛУБИНИ САҚЛАШ МАСАЛАСИГА ДОИР (О. ГЕНРИ ҲИКОЯЛАРИ МИСОЛИДА).....	52
11. Matkarimova Gulira'no Abdullayevna XALQ OG'ZAKI IJODI VA MIFOLOGIK MANBALARDA UCHRAYDIGAN FITONIMLARNING INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDAGI LEKSIK-SEMANTIK XUSUSIYATLARI.....	63
12. Алена Ялмагиевна Иванова ВЛИЯНИЕ КОНФУЦИАНСТВА НА ПРОЯВЛЕНИЕ ЭМОЦИЙ.....	68
13. Yunusova Gulshoda Dilshadovna EKVIVALENTLIK VA FE'L VALENSIYASI.....	80
14. Eshboyev Qahramon Bakir o'g'li O'ZBEK TILI SINONIMIK LUG'ATLARIDA DARAJALANISH METODOLOGIYASI.....	85
15. To'liboyeva Gulnura Baxadir qizi PEYZAJ BADIY VOSITA SIFATIDA (O'ZBEK VA QORAQALPOQ SHE'RIYATI MISOLIDA).....	91
16. Холбобоева Нилуфар Бахтиёр кизи НАВОИЙГА ТАХМИС.....	96
17. Сайымбетов Шарафатдин Уракбаевич И. ЮСУПОВНИНГ «ДАЛА АРМОНЛАРИ» ПОЭМАСИДА ИНДИВИДУАЛ МЕТАФОРЛАРНИНГ ҚЎЛЛАНИЛИШИ ВА БАДИИЙ ВАЗИФАЛАРИ.....	102
18. Комила Мамадиёрова ОНОМАСТИК БИРЛИКЛАРНИНГ ИНТЕГРАЦИОН ТАБИАТИ ХУСУСИДА.....	106
19. Xolova Muyassar Abdulhakimovna O'ZBEK SHEVALARIDA FONETIK O'ZGARISHLAR (Surxondaryo viloyati misolida).....	111
20. Malika Soliyeva INGLIZ TILIDAGI INTONATSIYANING AYRIM FONOSTILISTIK XUSUSIYATLARI.....	118
21. Комила Мамадиёрова ОНОМАСТИК БИРЛИКЛАРНИНГ УСЛУБИЙ ФУНКЦИЯЛАРИ ХУСУСИДА.....	122

22. Xurinsa Xudoyberdiyeva TROPLARNING USLUBIY XUSUSIYATI (Xosiyat Rustamova lirikasi misolida).....	128
23. Israilova Sayera Tashpulat qizi INTERFAOL USULLAR ORQALI INGLIZ TILIDA O‘QISH KO‘NIKMASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH (Tarix yo‘nalishi talabalari uchun).....	133
24. Israilova Sayera Tashpulat qizi INGLIZ XALQ ERTAKLARI ORQALI BOSHLANG‘ICH SINFI O‘QUVCHILARIDA O‘QISH KO‘NIKMASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH.....	137
25. Комила Мамадиёрова ОНОМАСТИК БИРЛИКЛАРНИНГ ИНТЕГРАЦИОН ТАБИАТИ ХУСУСИДА.....	143
26. Робиға Мамбетова ҚОЗОҒИСТОН ЎЗБЕКЛАРИ ФОЛЬКЛОР АСАРЛАРИНИНГ ЛИНГВОМАДАНИЙ ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ.....	149
27. Ҳамидулла Годжиев ТУРКИСТОН ЖАДИДЧИЛИК ҲАРАКАТИНИНГ УМУММАЪРИФИЙ – УМУМАДАБИЙ ТАМОЙИЛЛАРИ.....	154
28. Ergashova Rano Turaevna LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF AVIATION TERMINOLOGY IN ENGLISH, RUSSIAN, AND UZBEK LANGUAGES: SPECIFICITIES AND COMMONALITIES.....	160
29. Bobir Maxammadov MIKROSOFT VINDOVS OPERATSION TIZIMI TERMINLARINING LEKSIKOGRAFIK TAVSIFI MASALALARI: MUAMMOLAR VA VAZIFALAR.....	170
30. Xalimova Firuza Rustamovna POETIK MATNDA BADIY KONSEPTLAR VA METAFORALARNING KOGNITIV-ESTETIK TALQINI.....	176
31. Комила Мамадиёрова ОНОМАСТИК БИРЛИКЛАРНИНГ ИНТЕГРАЦИОН ТАБИАТИ ХУСУСИДА.....	182
32. Матлуба Шукурова ЭНАХОН СИДДИҚОВА ШЕЪРИЯТИДА “АЁЛ” КОНЦЕПТИНИНГ АКТУАЛЛАШУВИ.....	187
33. Tashkulova Zarnigor “SHARQ” KONSEPTI SEMANTIK MAYDONIDA PEYZAJNING IFODALANISHI (S. MOEM HIKOYALARI MISOLIDA).....	195

ISSN: 2181-9297

www.tadqiqot.uz

Karimova Dilorom ShavkatovnaAndijan State Pedagogical Institute,
Doctor of Philosophy in Philology, PhD
e-mail: karimovadilorom15@gmail.com**VERBAL AND NON-VERBAL INTERPRETATION OF THE CONCEPTS OF “DEATH”
AND “LIFE”** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17087343>**ABSTRACT**

Scientists interpret the concepts of verbal and non-verbal from different perspectives. The orderly placement of words with both positive and negative meanings in the dictionary of linguistic terms serves as one of the foundations of this study. The article focuses on one of the current problems in linguistics, the concept of death and its comparative analysis of the concepts of life and death. In the scientific article, we can see that the expression of death and life through verbal and non-verbal means is reflected in the examples of English and Uzbek.

Key words: Linguistic concepts, life, death, verbal, non-verbal, linguoculturology, ethno linguistics.

Каримова Дилором ШавкатовнаАндижанский государственный педагогический институт,
Доктор философии по филологии, Ph.D
e-mail: karimovadilorom15@gmail.com**ВЕРБАЛЬНАЯ И НЕВЕРБАЛЬНАЯ ИНТЕРПРЕТАЦИЯ КОНЦЕПТОВ
«СМЕРТЬ» И «ЖИЗНЬ»****АННОТАЦИЯ**

Ученые интерпретируют понятия вербального и невербального с разных точек зрения. Систематическое размещение слов с положительным и отрицательным значением в словаре лингвистических терминов служит одной из основ данного исследования. Статья посвящена одной из актуальных проблем в языкознании, концепту смерти и его сопоставительному анализу с концептами жизни и смерти. В научной статье мы видим, что выражение смерти и жизни посредством вербальных и невербальных средств отражено на примерах английского и узбекского языков.

Ключевые слова: Языковые концепты, жизнь, смерть, вербальный, невербальный, лингвокультурология, этнолингвистика.

Karimova Dilorom ShavkatovnaAndijon davlat pedagogika instituti,
Filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori PhD,
e-mail: karimovadilorom15@gmail.com**“O‘LIM” VA “HAYOT” KONSEPTLARINING VERBAL VA NOVERBAL TALQINI**

ANNOTATSIYA

Olimlar verbal va noverbal tushunchalarini turli nuqtai nazardan izohlaydilar. Tilshunoslik terminlari lugʻatida ijobiy va salbiy maʼnoli soʻzlarning tizimli joylashishi ushbu tadqiqotning asoslaridan biri boʻlib xizmat qiladi. Maqola tilshunoslikning dolzarb muammolaridan biri boʻlgan oʻlim tushunchasi va uning hayot va oʻlim tushunchalari bilan qiyosiy tahliliga bagʻishlangan. Ilmiy maqolada oʻlim va hayotning verbal va noverbal vositalar orqali ifodalanishi ingliz va oʻzbek tillari misollarida oʻz ifodasini topganligini koʻramiz.

Kalit soʻzlar: Til tushunchalari, hayot, oʻlim, verbal, noverbal, lingvomadaniyatshunoslik, etnolingvistika.

Introduction. Language is a linguistic unit with a complex structure and a multifaceted essence. It is natural for a person to influence it when using language, to learn to “**do it his way**”. Today, such areas as cognitive linguistics, psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics, pragmatics, linguoculturology, and ethno linguistics have an object of study, clearly defined goals, objectives, and methods of analysis. Even at the current stages of development of world linguistics, the study of language in connection with external factors such as the individual characteristics of the person using it, the situation in which speech activity is carried out, space, time, sociolinguistics, the environment, etc. has become one of the central issues. In Uzbek linguistics, serious attention is paid to studying language units in relation to external factors such as linguistic consciousness and thinking, psychology, gender, age characteristics, national-cultural orientations, and professional experience of the language users. By the 20th century, as noted by A. Nurmonov, the inclusion of the category of “**language personality**” in the scientific paradigm of linguistics led to the assimilation of concepts such as personality, consciousness, thinking, activity, behavior, and situation, which were previously excluded from linguistics, but were close to linguistics.

Language review. Associative relations of language units are based on the emergence of verbal and nonverbal relations. Issues such as the meaning and essence of associative relations, their introduction into scientific practice in science, the formation of an associative approach in language, and the study of verbal and nonverbal associative concepts are discussed. According to sources, the term “**association**” (Latin association – joining, attachment) was introduced into scientific practice in 1690 by the English philosopher, educator, representative of empiricism and liberalism J. Locke. He propagated the views on the association of ideas put forward by the great thinkers of the ancient world, Plato and Aristotle. Plato and Aristotle understood the process of memorization as a mechanism of association. Aristotle described the associative connection of ideas based on similarity, temporal sequence and contrast (opposition), while Plato provided information about the connections in memory based on similarity and proximity.

Associative verbal and non-verbal networks reveal connections between different levels of language, which allow for direct communication with other levels of language based on language units. These situations are expressed in the direct connection of the stimulus word with the lexical, morphological, syntactic, word-forming system of the word and in the interaction of associations. [1: 90-92]

The most important types of communication between people are verbal and non-verbal communication. Nonverbal communication is not based on the use of language, sound speech; it is communication through mimicry, gestures, pantomime, sensory or bodily communication. This is tactile, visual, auditory, olfactory, and other sensations and perceptions received from another person. Most of the nonverbal forms and means of human communication are innate and allow interaction not only with those similar to oneself, but with other living creatures by achieving consensus at the emotional and behavioral levels.

Verbal communication is inherent only to humans and determines the acquisition of language as a necessary condition. Speech as a means of communication is manifested both as a source of information and as a means of interaction with the interlocutor. It is necessary to remember the words of the great poet Saadi: “**Whether you have a mind or not, whether you are great or small, we do not know until you utter a word.**” Verbal (speech) communication includes the meaning and

essence of words, phrases. The main place is occupied by the accuracy of the use of the word, its expressiveness and universality, sounds, pronunciation of words, tone expression and essence. Time is of great importance for the philosophy of life - the essence of creation, development and formation. History, in turn, is manifested in the philosophy of life as unique and unrepeatable "cultural organisms" that go through processes similar to biological periodicity from birth to death. The historical process, unlike nature, where the law of causality reigns, is subject to fate. Later in the philosophy of life, the concept of "**mass society**" appeared; it leads the individual to lack of will, deprivation of creativity, and alienation. These views manifest themselves as a call to protect the culture of "**all people**" from the ideas of democracy and equality that were emerging at that time. For these reasons, Nietzsche considered generally accepted values and norms in the "natural" perspective of life n calls for reassessment, for following the ideal person who is the embodiment of the true "**life**" values. [2:]

Methodology. Human life encompasses spiritual, cognitive, aesthetic economic needs. The linguistic picture of the world is historically formed in the consciousness of the relevant language community and, having determined its stability in the language, finds its expression in linguistic expression. The concept of life is expressed **in Uzbek** with noun lexemes such as "hayot, tirikchilik, tiriklik, borlik, umr", **in English**: "life, livelihood, liveliness, life, existence", in phraseologisms and paremias it is also expressed in the images of forehead and, fate, destiny in fiction. Songs such as "**Peshonaga sizinda arilma yor**" are among them. When assessing life, the environment (economic, social, and political) of that time is taken into account. "**Hush durur Bog'u koinot durur, Barchadin sirinda Hayot guli**", A.Navoiy. "**Search for your purpose in your life, For within the abstract lies the jewel of knowledge,**" Anbar Atin. "**Life is action, inaction is death,**" Lewis Morris. "**Living means the submission of the body to perception and reason,**" Inb Sino. So, if Navoiy describes life as the highest quality, Anbar Atin emphasizes that living with a purpose is the law of life. [3: 35-48]

Through such oppositions as "**harm, benefit, illness, tension, elevation, weakness, strength, tension, sluggishness, denial of life, affirmation of life,**" the researcher draws attention to the heroic nature of optimism in life. The researcher considers "**pessimism**" a threat to life. In his opinion, everything that exists is life.

Life is assessed as a judge, life is a teacher, and life is an aggressor. A person is mainly subject to passive life. He can always blame and complain about it. However, modernity requires more mobility from a person, and this is mainly expressed in journalistic contexts: life is embodied as a partner; even life is embodied as a slave. Life can be studied by dividing it into these semantic fields: **in Uzbek**: "Human life is the highest value, Man is more expensive than gold, Man's hand is a flower, Man is a gem, and Man is the golden crown of the world. Being alive is happiness", **in English**: "Human life is the highest value, Man is more expensive than gold, Man's hand is a flower, Man is a gem, and Man is the golden crown of the world. Being alive is happiness". Because a person is the creator of any spiritual wealth. That is why there cannot be any value that is not dependent on the consciousness and activity of a person that is outside of him. After all, in Navoi's worldview and basis, a person is considered great.

"You have made everything seem so,
You have made everything noble."

In life, a person should always live with good intentions. Good intentions are half a state, Hope is immortal - risk is not small, Having one's place is alive, There is no grave for the dead, There is no net for the alive. A dog does not bite a dead wolf.

Maqsud Shayhzoda also said:

"There are lives that are more alive than dead,
There are people that are more dead than alive." [5: 200-208]

His lines are also a clear example of the views expressed above about the philosophy of life. Life is about movement. There is no rest for a living person. If you eat little, you will live long, if you work hard, you will grow much. Life is an attempt. For those who have not seen the egg, neither a crow nor a chicken.

It is necessary to fight for life. Before you jump into the river, find a way: if you have hope from Friday, start moving from Thursday: Eat your sorrow from the nose without time: a trap thrown from afar, reaches the right destination: Life is a struggle or a condition of life, if the struggle ends, life also ends. If there is no meaning and purpose in life, it will become more difficult. Survival in life is the growth of strength, the desire for power - it is intuitive and instinctive for humanity, and it is these values that threaten its value, and what gives meaning to life is the values. In the linguistic landscape of the world of language owners: Fate is the supreme judge. That is, life is a blessing given by God. A person moves towards the path that fate has led him to. At the same time, a person is manifested as the highest value. Therefore, a person exists in the human mind in the scheme of sociality, value-value-value-national-consciousness-language.

It is known that lexical and semantic units in the language are naturally revealed through adjacent meanings (close, opposite, similar meanings). For example, the opposite meaning of the lexeme “**life**” is expressed through the lexeme “**death**”. We can see the nonverbal expression of the concept of “**life**” in the English language in the following examples:

1. Lifes begin at forty - this expression, which is said to begin at forty, is related to the way of life of the English nation, and the English consider themselves perfectly ready for life and marriage at this age. In their opinion, if a person turns forty has the necessary skills, experience and tools to live a happy life, life will improve. “Today people in their fortieth are now able to get married, have children and prosper as the saying goes life begins at fouth”.
2. In the next life - the expression about life after death shows religious beliefs and the English believe that there is another life after death. “Each household may have left offerings for their ancestors goodwill or to sustain them in the next life”.
3. A daughter is a daughter all of her life – this lexeme describes the relationship of a girl with her parents, the family where she was born and raised. According to them, even after a girl gets married, her love and care for her family remain the same. Boys, on the other hand, usually become more attached to their family after they get married. “You will always be my little girl, a son is son until, he takes a wife, a daughter is a daughter all of her life”. [8:]

What are verbal devices? In linguistics, verbal means are understood as communication that is carried out using words in the process of communication, while nonverbal means are understood as expressing one's thoughts without using speech through a number of means, such as gestures, body parts (hands, sometimes legs, body movements, shoulders, lip gestures, eyes and eyebrows, facial movements, head movements), in addition to words. However, like verbal communication, it is possible to clearly see the negative and positive sides of nonverbal communication. These are communication processes that can affect both consciously and even unconsciously. In this regard, according to the English scientists Cohen and Harrison, “in the implementation of communication by verbal means, people can be far from each other, this can be expressed through telephone or fax, letter messages, but in order to express themselves through non-verbal means, they must see each other and understand the gestures they are making, so communicating through verbal means is easier than non-verbal communication.” For example, the concept of “**death**” consists of the content of signs and characteristics belonging to humans, plants, the animal world, social and psychological states, etc., which include the end of life, the cessation of the function of a body part important for life, the state of the death process, the cause of death, plague, physical and mental peace and quiet, the growth or destruction of an inanimate object, passing away, taking one's last thing, etc. The concept of “death” has unusual features, some of which are part of its structure, and are found in speech situations. **For example:** a funeral - “dead.....”, the quietest, calmest time....., a very tired, exhausted, and powerless law - a dead law, a used, no longer usable thing - a dead copy, a stagnant (pond) water - dead water, a cigarette flame - a dead fire, a tasteless - a dead wine, Azrael - death angel, a set time limit - deadline, US paper money - dead president (sl.). As can be seen from the above examples, the concept of “death” has various typical and unusual features, arising from the requirements of the concept and the choice of the communicants (interlocutors), and occurring in accordance with the linguistic and life experience of the participants in the dialogue. [9:]

The word death is considered the main frequency of use in this work and is used a lot because its use is metaphorical. As for the title of the work, “Morality play” has a much broader meaning than its meaning, it is a phraseological unit. The main meaning in the work is considered to be the use of art in solving a crime. As can be seen, the concept of life and death remains relevant for all stages of human development, analyzing the novel “Morality play”, we can see that the conceptual features of life and death are revealed in it in the form of heroes, linking them to art.

Conclusion. Verbal and nonverbal lexemes the concepts of death and life in English and Uzbek are reflected not only in social life, but also in unreal phenomena. This is not only for life, but also for inanimate objects, we can certainly see the lexemes of death and life in the root of the meanings of beginning and end. According to initial data, the concept of isomorphism appeared and was used in the system of natural sciences. Later, this concept began to be used in other fields of science, in particular, philosophy, and then in linguistics.

Scientists interpret the concepts of isomorphism and allomorphy from different perspectives. The orderly placement of words with both positive and negative meanings in the dictionary of linguistic terms serves as one of the foundations of this study. In clinical and biological processes, we can see that similar and dissimilar aspects of death and life are of great importance in the process of human life.

Reference

1. A.Nurmonov. Lingvistil ta’limotning yangi bosqichi. Tanlangan asarlar. III jild. – Toshkent: Akademnashr, 2012. – B. 92.
2. Философский энциклопедический словарь. 2010 // dic.academic.ru // dic. nsf/ enc. Philosophy/1978. G‘oziyev E.G. Umumiy psixologiya. Toshkent. 2002.1-2 kitob.
3. Еврейский вопрос, как вопрос о расовом характере и о его вредоносном влиянии на существование народов, на нравы и культуру. / Перевод 5-го издания. — М., 1906. С. – 35-48
4. Иланова О.А. Концепт “жизнь” в русской языковой картине в мире; лингвокультурологический и лексикографический аспекты. Автореферат. (дис.кан.наук) Санк-Петербургб 2005. С 28.
5. Komilova G.R. Hayot buyuk qadriyat sifatida. NamDu Ilmiy habarnomasi 2021.2. B. -208
6. <https://idioms.thefreedictionary.com/life>.
7. <https://merriam.webster.com/dictionary.the.next.life>
8. Cohen & Harrison, 1972 University of Twente P.O.Box 217, 7500AE Enschede the Netherlands.
9. By Jack London “A Daughter Of The Snows” www.freeclassicebooks.com

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

8 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 8, НОМЕР 2

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 8, ISSUE 2

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000